

MACHINE LEARNING-DRIVEN STOCK MARKET PREDICTION USING REINFORCEMENT LEARNING TECHNIQUES

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Abstract:

The large amount of data is generated everyday and it becomes very challenging to compile, analyse and making out decisions. Big Data Analytics is a boon to deal with this. Profiteering in Stock market is not an easy task because of its dynamic in nature. When to buy or sell the stocks is to be determined cautiously and thus, the massive amount of data (Big Data) used to process and formulate valuable information for correct decision making. Various algorithmic techniques has been developed and under application to improve stock trading. In this paper, Deep Learning algorithms are applied to predict different stock data values processing large amount of unstructured or unsupervised data. The five important features that define Big Data are its volume, value, variety, velocity and veracity.

Keywords: *Deep Learning, Reinforcement Learning, Stock trading, Deep Q-learning, Double DQN, Dueling Double DQN.*

Introduction

Optimal decision making in trading is not an easy task. A lot of investigation has to be done with stock data sets and several quantitative techniques to be applied for in-depth study. In this process, a large number of indicators with machine learning and deep learning techniques [1] such as linear regression [4, 5, 6], Moving averages [2, 3], neural networks [7, 8], Recurrent neural network [9, 10, 11, 12] and Reinforcement learning (RL) are implemented to predict the stock prices movements and strategies [13, 14]. When these techniques are applied on several data sets times and again, the results shows that in comparison to the traditional indicators and method the advanced artificial neural network perform with better accuracy [15, 16].

There are several reasons for unpredictability of stock prices with high accuracy. First and foremost is the stock market changes in no time, i.e., very rapidly changes, secondly the appropriate useful data availability is also not sufficient, i.e., incomplete information at hand and thirdly, there is no standard tools and techniques which guarantees for correct prediction in all situation. Reinforcement learning is one of the methods to solve such complex decision problems. The best way therefore that mostly believes is trial and error, i.e., the loop to conduct experiments and store experiences. Reinforcement learning work on above principle and thus can prove to be a better choice for stock price prediction [17]. Deep Learning methods are significant to extract features from high dimensional data and provide hidden patterns. However, it somehow lacks the decision-making capabilities. Thus, When the Deep Learning approach is combined with the decision making ability of Reinforcement Learning, it must yield better results. RL techniques contribute to solve the algorithmic trading problem. Recurrent Reinforcement Learning algorithm have been found to give good results without the need to build forecasting models [18]. The foreign exchange market also using Adaptive Reinforcement Learning (ARL) to trade [19]. The investigation results of recent times shows researchers found interesting in using Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL) method to solve the algorithmic trading problem [20, 21, 22, 23, 24, 20, 25].

A key focus of DRL in financial analysis is the development of fully autonomous systems that mimic a financial advisor or a financial analyst, in terms of analysis and decision making for financial tasks such as trading. DRL in finance can be used by agents to make optimal policy decisions in order to receive the maximal cumulative reward or return [28]. Here, the agent collects information about the current state and tries to approximate its value using a neural network, which should lead towards an optimal decision [29].

All the reinforcement learning (RL) algorithms can be classified in several families depending on whether the algorithm explicitly learns and/or uses the environment dynamics or whether they are off-policy or on-policy. If the algorithm uses environment dynamics during the decision making process, then it is known as a model based algorithm, otherwise when it doesn't make use of them, it is known as model free. Similarly, the off-policy algorithms learn a value function independently from the agent's decisions. This means that the behavior policy and the target policy can be different. The DQN, Double DQN and Dueling DQN, all are model free and off-policy.

In the present paper, DRL is applied on ten randomly selected datasets from Indian stock market to automate the stock trading and to maximize the gain. Model is trained with historical stock data by using Deep Q-Network (DQN), Double Deep Q-Network (DDQN) and Dueling Double Deep Q-Network (Dueling DDQN) to predict the stock trading strategy for holding, buying and selling the stocks. The unseen data from the later period is used for validation of the model and performance is evaluated and compared.

Research Methodology: Stock prediction in this paper is based on 3 main algorithm; Deep Q-Network, Double Deep Q-Network and Duelling Double Deep Q-Network [26].

2.1 Deep Q-Network: It is a simple, classical but powerful algorithm of DRL and its model architecture may be shown as:

$$Q_{target} = r_{t+1} + \gamma \max_{a'} [Q(s'_t, a'_t; \theta)]$$

where, Q_{target} is the target Q value obtained using the Bellman Equation and θ denotes the parameters of the Q-Network, $Q(s_t; a_t)$ is the expected future reward.

The Deep Q-Network is a model-free reinforcement learning that can deal with sequential decision making. The goal here is to learn an optimal policy that maximizes the reward or gain. The agent depends on the current state of the environment and rewards from the environment to takes appropriate action. The previous state experiences are stored along with the previous states, actions, rewards. To avoid over fitting, the data from stored memory is sampled randomly and fed to the train network in small batch sizes. One major difference between the Deep Q-Network and the Convolution Neural Network (known as Q-Network) is a new Target-Q-Network as given above.

Optimal Q-value or the action-value pair is computed each time to select and measure the actions. The max of all the actions are employed in the Deep Q-Network which leads to overestimation of the Q-value and the errors keeps on accumulating [27]. Thus, Double DQN is used to solve this problem of overestimation of Q-value. Double DQN implement another neural network that optimizes the influence of error.

Double Deep Q-Network

Double DQN uses two neural networks to provide more stability to the target values for update. One is the main network and the target network with same structure as in DQN. Here, the action is selected based on the main Q-Network but the target Q-network work to correspond to select and measure the actions and supply that particular state-action for updation. Thus, all possible actions in the present state is taken from the main Q-Network and which is updated at each time step. Then, all the state-action values of such possible actions are taken in the function argmax (Eq 2), and that specific action is selected where the state-action value maximizes the output.

$$Q_{target} = r_{t+1} + \gamma Q(s_t, \text{argmax}_{a'} Q(s'_t, a'_t; \theta); \theta')$$

The problems of overestimation and instability in Q-values can be overcome with two neural networks as above.

Dueling Double Deep Q-Network

Both DQN as well as in Double DQN there is one main network and one target where the network values are copied periodically from the main network's values. The speciality of Duelling Double DQN is its non-sequential network architecture. Here the convolution layers get separated into two streams where both the sub-networks are fully connected layer and output layers. The first sub-network estimate the value of the given state and the second sub-network estimates the merit value of taking a particular action comparing with the base value in the current state.

$$Q(s_t, a_t; \theta, \alpha, \beta) = V(s_t; \theta, \beta) + (A(s_t, a_t; \theta, \alpha) - \max_{a' \in |A|} A(s_t, a'_t; \theta, \alpha))$$

Where A is the advantage value, V is the state-value, θ is common parameter, α and β are the parameter vectors of the Advantage sub-network and State-Value function respectively. The value of that state which is estimated from the state-value (V) plus the advantage of taking that action in that state gives us the Q value for a given state-action pair.

The above equation can be written as :

$$Q(s_t, a_t; \theta, \alpha, \beta) = V(s_t; \theta, \beta) + (A(s_t, a_t; \theta, \alpha))$$

If we know the value of S and A, we can get the Q-value easily, but we cannot get the values of S and A if Q-value is known. To increase the stability of the algorithm, the last part of the above equation may be written as :

$$Q(s_t, a_t; \theta, \alpha, \beta) = V(s; \theta, \beta) + (A(s_t, a_t; \theta, \alpha) - \frac{1}{|A|} \sum_{a'} A(s_t, a'_t; \theta, \alpha))$$

Figure 1: Deep Q-Network model architecture

Data Collection, Analysis and Results:

We collected 10 Indian stock dataset from National Stock Exchange (NSE) India, that consists of the price history and trading volumes of stocks in the index NIFTY 50 from the period 01.01.2003 to 31.12.202. Then, Deep Q-Network(DQN), Double Deep Q-Network (DDQN), and Dueling Double Deep Q-Network (Dueling DDQN) is employed to automate the stock trading and to maximize the gain. In this process, the dataset has been divided for training and testing purpose in equal proportions and fed to the models. The train and test rewards and profits are estimated and compared.

Agent Training

As we know the Q-Network has input, hidden and output layers and to obtain the optimal weights, the hyper parameters are tuned as per equation (1). In time-series problems it is very crucial for the long-term reward. The Q-Network is trained by minimizing the loss function as given below:

$$L(\theta) = E[(Q_{target} - Q(s_t, a_t; \theta))^2]$$

The learning rate is 0:00025 and the optimizer is Adam optimizer. The training is done for 50 episodes with batch size of 64 and the agent performs three actions: hold, buy and sell.

(Figure 2 Plot showing train and test dataset of ULTRACEMCO stock price)

Table 1: Model hyperparameters

Hyperparameters	Values
Window size	90
Batch size	64
Episodes	50
Gamma	0.95
Epsilon	1
Learning rate	0.00025
Epsilon minimum	0.1
Epsilon decay	0.995
Optimizer	Adam
Loss function	Mean square error

Agent Testing

The unseen test dataset of later periods are taken for the testing of the agent and the performance of the agent is measured in terms of total profit. The profit is calculated by sale price - purchase price.

Empirical Results

In this research, ten Indian stock datasets and three deep Q-networks are employed to perform the experiments. Training to each dataset is done on train data and then tested on the unseen test data. Three deep reinforcement learning models (DQN, Double DQN and Dueling DDQN) are employed to find total rewards and profit from training data and test data using ten Indian stocks as shown in Table 2,3,4 respectively.

Figure 2 shows the train and test data used for each dataset. One stock dataset (ULTRACEMCO dataset) is selected randomly and the train and test data are plotted along with the training loss and training rewards with respect to number of epochs for DQN (Figure 2-a,b). MSE (Mean square error) is used to calculate the loss that estimates the difference between the actual and predicted values. Figure 2c shows the time-market value of the DQN model corresponding to the ULTRACEMCO dataset. Red, green and blue points corresponds to hold, buy and sell the stock respectively. Similarly, Figure 3-a,b,c shows the training loss, training rewards and time-market value for the ULTRACEMCO dataset using Double DQN. Figure 4-a,b,c shows the training loss, training rewards and time-market value for the ULTRACEMCO dataset using Dueling Double DQN.

(Figure 2-a Train Loss w.r.t. Number of epochs for DQN)

(Figure 2-b Train Reward w.r.t. Number of epochs for DQN)

(Figure 2-C Time-Market Value for DQN)

(a)

(b)

(Figure 3-a,b Train Loss and Train Reward w.r.t. Number of epochs for DDQN)

(Figure 3-c time-market value for DDQN)

(a)

(b)

(Figure 4-a,b Train Loss and Train Reward w.r.t. Number of epochs for Dueling DDQN)

(Figure 4-c Time-Market value for Dueling DDQN)

Table -2(Rewards and profit obtained using DQN)

Dataset	Train Rewards	Train Profit	Test Rewards	Test Profit
ULTRACEMCO	212	8838	19	25206
TECHM	-404	78	-387	-659
ZEEL	312	6652	132	2946
RELIANCE	126	17119	-62	1262
TCS	258	12402	28	4794
UPL	193	3692	98	4842
TATAMOTORS	224	10519	29	25202
TATASTEEL	238	3502	48	61
POWERGRID	208	1162	68	826
NESTLEIND	-138	11795	-162	16405

Table -3 (Rewards and profit obtained using Double DQN)

Dataset	Train Rewards	Train Profit	Test Rewards	Test Profit
ULTRACEMCO	38	672	335	57647
TECHM	-12	71	5	225
ZEEL	-3	21	6	18
RELIANCE	-162	0	-201	55
TCS	238	14966	289	39021
UPL	13	423	13	665
TATAMOTORS	61	702	72	992
TATASTEEL	32	1162	-3	4
POWERGRID	146	-156	149	802
NESTLEIND	5	8568	6	22028

Table -4 (Rewards and profit obtained using Dueling Double DQN)

Dataset	Train Rewards	Train Profit	Test Rewards	Test Profit
ULTRACEMCO	116	7098	29	6242
TECHM	53	25989	93	14849
ZEEL	39	1688	128	2798
RELIANCE	348	29361	329	29712
TCS	56	3481	99	17159
UPL	112	7994	168	10262
TATAMOTORS	238	16568	171	8286
TATASTEEL	2	19	6	23
POWERGRID	48	544	96	101684
NESTLEIND	121	43878	96	1224

Conclusion

In view of above, the deep reinforcement learning may be used to automate trade execution and generate profit. The performance of the DRL in solving stock market strategy problems is analysed and three DRL networks: DQN, DDQL and Dueling DDQN are compared for 10 Indian stock datasets. The result shows that the three deep learning algorithms perform well in solving the decision-making problems of stock market. Further, It may be stated that the algorithms perform better than traditional methods. A thorough observation reveals that on an average the Dueling DDQN network performed better than DDQN and DQN, and Double DQN performed better than DQN.

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